

HAVING PRE-WARM-UP ACTIVITIES IN THE CLASSROOM IN ESL AND THE BENEFITS COMES WITHIN IT

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ABSTRACT

The world is changing day by day and it is becoming harder and harder for students to study by traditional methods of teaching, which makes teachers to research and find new ways for their students.

The main aim of this article is to focus on having pre-warm-up activities in the classroom and to discuss the benefits of this. Most teachers do just warm-up activities themselves, but in a classroom it is essential to have both pre-warm-up and warm-up activities. The most benefits are psychological and directly connected with the brain function.

Key words: brain function, greeting, sports exercise, get energized, English atmosphere, pre-warm-up activities, warm-up activities;

INTRODUCTION

It is pivotal that usually the lesson should get started with a few of warm-up activities in order to make students adapt the English atmosphere faster. However, before this process, there also lies a number of occasions which I call to be pre-warm-up activities. Most ESL teachers limit themselves and do not pay enough attention to such kind of activities. As a result, the lessons are likely to remain traditional. For me, as a young teacher, I consider that it is more than important to have such pre-warm-up called things. In this, children do not necessarily need to be told that they are having them, but just it is the only person, teacher, who should know it well. So, it is natural to give a question of what is pre-warm-up activities are? For this question, my answer would be like this: the things that happens in a classroom from the time teacher puts a foot into the class until she comes to warm up activities. Actually, these stuffs include greeting between teacher and students, students sitting in the classroom, taking their stuff like notebooks, books and pens, as well if some do, a short sports exercise. In this paper work, I will count the advantage sides of the things that happens during pre-warm-up activities.

MAIN PART

“Warm-up activities for English classes are an important teaching tool and often make or break a lesson. With that in mind, we’ll give you some easy warm-ups you can incorporate into your virtual or physical classroom!” (Johanna Kawasaki, 2021);

Well, actually the more things get involved in this time, the more benefits are highly likely to appear. But depending on the teacher, it can be quite different. First of all,

✚ It increases children’s mood

The reason for this, when the teacher enters the classroom, teacher can always greet his/her children with a face with smile, which slows down children’s fears and worries for the day. Once the lesson is started with smile, it literally in most cases, continues with smile. To better it, teacher can even say or ask their state, health and such things with giving a few questions like “How are you?” “How are you doing?”

✚ Children can use this time for fun

Almost in every classroom in our country, there is a habit of checking children’s attendance to the lesson at the first 5 minutes of the lesson. When teacher reads each child’s name one by one, children can just sit down and do nothing having fun in case they get tired of the previous lesson. In this situation, even most children themselves really like their teaching checking pupils’ attendance and putting absence marks to the register.

✚ Teacher will have some time to breath and think clearly

In most cases, all the attention is given to the children and teachers are forgotten. I think in classroom, it is more important for the teacher to have some pauses while teaching, otherwise, the lesson might become of poor quality. Therefore, while ordering children to get their stuff and home task ready, teacher can spare a few minutes about the class and his/her lesson plan for the lesson.

✚ Children get energized

Most often, only a very few limited numbers of classrooms have the ventilation facilities, which make it harder for the children to stay energized. This is because while the brains of children do not receive enough oxygen levels, they immediately start to feel sleepy and lose their concentration on the lesson. So, to avoid it the best way would be to have a short-2-minute exercises with children in the classroom.

“Warm-up sports are critical within side the English classroom. Students frequently come to elegance worn-out or with different matters on their minds, so it’s suitable to ease them into a category in preference to straight away hitting

them with a worrying grammar or vocabulary task. With a very good hotter you may placed your college students into English mode – attentive, involved and geared up to participate.” (Paul Newman, 2015);

What is required in this case is just the desire to stand up and stretch a little bit, which really gives fun to the children as well makes them more energized. Not only this, but also from medical point of view, such set of exercises tend to avoid anemia, back pain, poor eyesight and such things which are very common for children to have in this day and age.

“When starting a language lesson, it is important for you as the teacher to get your students into the right mindset first. This applies to all ages and levels. ESL warm-up activities for adults may differ a little from ESL games and activities for kids and teens, but they are of the same importance.” (Johanna Kawasaki, 2021);

After doing such things, teacher can follow his/her lesson with warm-up activities and have good time with children. All the views above are personal experiences and opinions of the author as well as made up by the observations of famous researchers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is really important to have pre-warm-up in the classroom. It may not hold so much value to other lessons like math, physics and others, but for English language teaching it is just impossible to express its significance with just a few words. Because English demands children to have a lot of both life and general skills like a pure mind to think, concentration to understand, interest and burning desire to learn and other a few things. Thus, every teacher needs to know about the benefits of pre-warm-up activities and use in their classes to get the best results out of it.

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